

ELECTRICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF POLY(VINYLIDENE FLUORIDE) NANOFIBRILLAR MATERIALS

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1 Introduction

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) has been recognised as an attractive material for many applications due to its electroactive properties as well as excellent mechanical strength, flexibility, easy conformability, and good processability [1]. Among its promising electrical properties, the ferro- and piezo-electric properties have drawn great attention in recent years. These two electrical properties are strongly influenced by molecular structures, especially molecular dipole alignment which can be induced by specific manufacturing methods. Depending on processing conditions, PVDF can exhibit five polymorphic modifications: α -, β -, γ -, δ - and ϵ -phase. Among the five phases, β -, γ - and δ -phase show a net polarisation with dipole alignment when PVDF crystalline molecular chains are packed into crystal lattices [2]. The β -phase polymorph of PVDF has the strongest ferro- and piezo-electric properties with the highest spontaneous polarisation and can be used for various applications, namely sensors, actuators and energy harvesters [3]. This polar phase can be generated by means of mechanical stretching and/or applying a high electric field to obtain desirable molecular orientation [4]. Furthermore, superior mechanical performance can also be achieved by the mechanical stretching process resulting in nanosized fibres [5]. There are various methods capable of producing continuously drawn fibrous structures: electrospinning and the concept of micro-/nano-fibrillar composites are the two chosen in this study to produce the required materials.

The electrospinning technique has been established as a simple and versatile method for fabrication of highly drawn polymer fibres with diameters of micro- or nano-metres [1, 6-8]. Electrospinning was first discovered by Rayleigh in 1897 [9] and highly oriented nanofibres can be produced from polymer solutions subjected to a mechanical drawing by using a strong electric field. Continuous fibres can be interconnected with each other to form a non-

woven final product. The structure and size of the fibres are significantly influenced by different electrospinning parameters employed.

Micro- or nano-fibrillar composites (MFCs or NFCs) concept uses two thermodynamically immiscible polymers, one of which later becomes an isotropic matrix and the other a reinforcing component. NFCs are manufactured via extrusion of melt blended polymers, cold drawing for fibrillation, and post processing for isotropisation of the major component [10]. The highly drawn nanofibrils can be isolated from the NFCs by dissolving the matrix component [11] and further processed to become a single polymer composite (SPC).

The main objective of this work was to measure and compare the electrical and mechanical properties of PVDF nanofibrillar single polymer composite (NF-SPC) and the electrospun PVDF nanofibre mat. Furthermore, different characterisation methods were conducted to identify the polymorphic modification of PVDF nanofibres for enhanced electrical properties.

2 Experimental Details

2.1 Materials

For producing the NFC structured material, linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE) (Qamar FC 12 HS, supplied by Eastern Petrochemical Company, Saudi Arabia) and commercial grade PVDF (Kynar[®] 720, supplied by Arkema Ltd, USA) were used as the matrix and reinforcement components, respectively. Xylene was then used in a Soxhlet apparatus to dissolve LLDPE for extracting PVDF nanofibrils for the subsequent preparation of PVDF NF-SPC.

To prepare a polymer solution for electrospinning, dimethyl formamide (DMF) was used as an active solvent to be mixed with acetone for dissolving the PVDF powder.

2.2 Electrospinning

PVDF pellets were ground to fine powders to facilitate dissolution prior to mixing with the

solvents. The solution with a PVDF concentration of 20 wt.% was prepared using a solvent mixture of DMF and acetone with a 50/50 volume ratio. 4.5 mL of PVDF solution was placed in a 5mL hypodermic glass syringe with a 0.9 mm needle and then fitted onto a syringe pump for controlled release of PVDF solution. The solution jet was deposited on a metallic mesh using a 12 kV voltage between the mesh plate and the syringe with a feed rate of 1.5 mL/h to produce a nanofibre mat. The travelling distance of the solution jet between the collecting mesh and the needle tip was set to be 10 cm. At the end of electrospinning, the formed fibre mat was carefully removed from the screen with the help of blown air to keep the integrity of the sample.

2.3 Nanofibrillar Composites Production

Dried LLDPE and PVDF pellets were manually mixed with a weight ratio of 70/30 and then extruded using a PRISM TSE 16 PC extruder with a heating zone temperature of 200°C, which is higher than the melting point of the two components. The extruded fibres were cold-drawn at room temperature between two winders with different rotating speeds to achieve a draw ratio of approximately 6.

In order to obtain only PVDF fibrils from the drawn LLDPE/PVDF blend filament, LLDPE was dissolved by boiling Xylene in a Soxhlet apparatus. Hot compaction of the extracted PVDF nanofibrils was carried out in a hydraulic press (Carver 4332-Indiana) initially at 148°C and cooled down to room temperature gradually to manufacture SPC. On cooling, the partially molten fibrils (mainly in the skin layer) recrystallise to form the matrix of the composite and bind the remaining fibrillar structure together as the reinforcement to form the SPC[12].

2.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The morphologies of electrospun PVDF and NF-SPC specimens were examined using a Philips XL30S FEG SEM machine with a maximum magnification of 80,000x to confirm the nano-sized fibrils and the SPC structure.

2.5 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy – Attenuated Total Reflectance (FTIR-ATR)

In this study, the α -phase and the β -phase of PVDF polymorphic modification were identified using a Thermo Electron Nicolet 8700 FTIR spectrometer with a Smart Orbit ATR Single Reflection accessory. PVDF thin film specimens were set on an ATR fixture and scanned from 4000 to 525 cm^{-1} . A

standard software, Omnic ESP version 7.1, was used to carry out measurement setting, data acquisition and analysis. Diamond was selected as the ATR crystal due to its durability and chemical inertness [13].

The fraction of β -phase polymorphic modification can be calculated according to specific absorption of α - and β -phase in FTIR spectra based on the Lambert-Beer law, Eq. (1) [14, 15].

$$F(\beta) = \frac{A_{\beta}}{1.3 A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{α} and A_{β} are the absorption bands for α - and β -phase in FTIR spectra, respectively. Peak areas in the FTIR spectrum corresponding to α -phase (765 cm^{-1}) and β -phase (840 cm^{-1}) were measured using a built-in curve fitting function of the analytical software.

2.6 Poling and Electric Measurement

In order to increase the dipole alignment to enhance the electrical properties, poling of specimens was carried out using a thermal poling method prior to the electrical tests. A specimen connected to the electrodes was immersed in silicone oil heated to 100°C and subjected to 150 MV/m DC power for one hour. After that, the film was cooled down to room temperature while maintaining the same electric field to retain the dipole alignment. Otherwise, the dipole could return to the original alignment.

Measurement of the frequency dependent capacitance was carried out using a Agilent 4294A Precision Impedance Analyzer (Agilent Technology Ltd, Japan) based on the piezoelectric resonance method. The machine can detect the natural frequency (resonant frequency) and the dimensional change of a piezoelectric material by using a scanning frequency between 40 Hz and 100 MHz in the alternating current (AC) electric field.

2.7 Mechanical Tests

Following the ASTM standard D882-09, ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and tensile modulus were measured using a computer controlled Instron Universal Testing Machine with a 30 kN load cell and 10 mm/min crosshead speed. All the tests were at least repeated 5 times and the average value of the

test results with an appropriate error bar have been presented.

3 Results

3.1 Morphology of Electrospun Mat and NF-SPC

It is clear that electrospun PVDF nanofibrils, of approximately 70 nm in diameter, in a 3-dimensional structure were produced. The interconnected fibrils formed a porous network structure (Fig. 1). Most of the fibres were well drawn with a uniform diameter along their entire length without any branching fibres.

NF-SPC manufactured from the extracted PVDF fibrils has been shown to have highly oriented nanofibrils with a high aspect ratio of around 150, Fig. 2. It is also clearly shown that the entire composite structure has been bonded by the partially molten PVDF acting as matrix material within the NF-SPC. The diameter of the fibrillar entity can be measured to be approximately 150 nm. Both of these structures demonstrate potential of possessing electrical properties with their drawn morphology. Further analyses have been carried out on the crystal structure and electrical properties for verification.

3.2 β -phase Crystal Structure

After poling treatment, the presence of β -phase peaks at 840 cm^{-1} and 1278 cm^{-1} in infrared spectra can be easily observed for the NF-SPC and the electrospun PVDF (Fig. 3). On the other hand, α -phase peaks representing isotropic PVDF, which can be clearly seen in the undrawn PVDF, either have been significantly reduced or can hardly be observed from the two manufactured nanofibrillar materials. This shows the successful modification of the crystal structure by the drawing of the materials during the manufacturing process to enhance the dipole alignment of the molecules as proven in the literature [4].

The fraction of β -phase was calculated using Eq. (1) from the spectrum of each of the materials. The undrawn PVDF and the NF-SPC have 50% and 85.5% of β -phase, respectively. This remarkable difference was due to the effects of mechanical stretching and poling for NF-SPC. Furthermore, the β -phase fraction of the electrospun PVDF is 100% as its spectrum does not reveal any peak corresponding to α -phase polymorphism on 765 cm^{-1} and 976 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 1 Microscopy of electrospun PVDF

Fig. 2 Microscopy of PVDF NF-SPC

Fig. 3 FTIR spectra of: (a) undrawn PVDF, (b) PVDF NF-SPC, and (c) electrospun PVDF.

3.3 Piezoelectric Property

From the impedance analysis, the piezoelectric resonance peak from the capacitance-frequency (C-F) curve was detected from poled NF-SPC and

electrospun PVDF in the frequency range from 10 to 20 MHz. Even though the peak is small (Fig. 4), the piezoelectric resonance behaviour has been markedly increased compared to that of undrawn PVDF which has a pretty smooth C-F curve (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 C-F curve of: (a) PVDF NF-SPC, and (b) electrospun PVDF

The two materials in Fig.4 show the change of curve at the same range of frequency between 14 and 16 MHz which is corresponding to the natural frequency of PVDF. The presence of weak resonance peaks in the C-F curve indicates the presence of piezoelectric/ferroelectric property. With further improvement in this property, useful applications as sensors or actuators would be possible.

Fig. 5 C-F curve of undrawn PVDF

3.4 Mechanical Properties

Due to the porous structure of the electrospun PVDF (Fig. 1), the reported values for mechanical properties was adjusted by taking into account the effective cross-section area. Assuming that the fibres

in a porous sample are all aligned along the testing direction, the effective cross-section area can be calculated comparing the weights of a solid and a porous sample occupying the same volume. The adjusted mechanical properties can then be compared to other materials on a similar base. UTS of the electrospun PVDF and PVDF NF-SPC were improved by 89% and 304%, respectively compared to isotropic PVDF (undrawn) (Fig. 6). Measurement of tensile modulus for PVDF NF-SPC also shows 38.6% increase (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6 Comparison of the UTS results

Fig. 7 Comparison of the tensile modulus

The failure mechanism of PVDF NF-SPC was identified to be delamination. It is believed the bonding of the nanofibrils by the partially molten PVDF from hot compaction was not strong enough to hold the fibrils together during tensile test. Judging from the observed failure of samples, Fig. 8, the separation of fibril strands under tension resulted from shear induced by the uneven amount of stretch in the longitudinal (fibrillar) direction. Furthermore, it can also be predicted that transverse strength of

this material will be poor due to the weaker bonding among fibrils.

Fig. 8 Failure mode of (a) LLDPE/PVDF NFC, (b) electrospun PVDF and (c) NF-SPC

4 Conclusions

- a. The selection of LLDPE as the matrix constituent provided high drawability of the immiscible blend with PVDF at room temperature and resulted in the significant reduction of fibrillar diameter. PVDF nanofibrils in the range of 150 nm were observed after NF-SPC manufacturing. Furthermore, the electrospun PVDF fibres had extremely fine diameters of approximately 70 nm, and were dispersed randomly, forming a porous structure.
- b. In the FTIR spectra, the PVDF NF-SPC and the electrospun PVDF both had the β -phase peaks developed by mechanical drawing and thermal poling. The electrospun nanofibrillar PVDF in particular showed only the β -phase peaks in the FTIR spectra without any visible α -phase peak.
- c. The PVDF NF-SPC and its electrospun counterpart showed clear improvement of the piezoelectric property through the presence of the resonance peak.
- d. The PVDF NF-SPC had 38.6 and 304% higher values of the tensile modulus and the UTS than the isotropic PVDF film. The adjusted UTS of the electrospun PVDF based on the effective cross-section, was increased by 89%.

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6 References

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